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SCIENTIFIC STUDY OF THE EVOLUTION AND PHYSICOCHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF SALTWORT IN THE FERGANA VALLEY

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Abstract: *The Fergana Valley in space and time, as well as in the soil profile individually according to the conditions of their formation, differs from other regions of Uzbekistan (Mirzachul, Jizzakh desert, Zeravshan and Vakhsh valleys). The accumulation of salts and geochemical compounds is the result of a complex set of ancient and modern processes, it was formed over many centuries of geological periods. The genesis, evolution and geochemistry of saline soils, including solonchaks, are very diverse. One of them, and the most important, is the parent rock, which is common in dry climates and contains various types of migrating salts. This causes salts in the topsoil to move from one place to another in the form of fine dust under the influence of wind or precipitation.*

Keywords: *Fergana Valley, Central Fergana, salt marsh, province, sulfate, carbonate*

НАУЧНОЕ ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ЭВОЛЮЦИИ И ФИЗИКО-ХИМИЧЕСКИХ СВОЙСТВ СОЛЯНКИ ФЕРГАНСКОЙ ДОЛИНЫ

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Аннотация: *Ферганская долина в пространстве и времени, а также по профилю почв в отдельности по условиям их формирования отличается от других регионов Узбекистана (Мирзачульской, Джизакской пустыни, Зеравшанской и Вахиской долин). Накопление солей и геохимических соединений является результатом сложного комплекса древних и современных процессов, оно формировалось на протяжении многих веков геологических периодов. Генезис, эволюция и геохимия засоленных почв, в том числе солончаков, весьма разнообразны. Одна из них, и самая важная, — материнская порода, распространенная в засушливом климате и содержащая различные виды мигрирующих солей. Это приводит к тому, что соли в верхнем слое почвы под действием ветра или осадков перемещаются из одного места в другое в виде мелкой пыли*

Ключевые слова: *Ферганская долина, Центральная Фергана, солончаки, провинция, сульфат, карбонат*

Scientific research into the genesis, evolution and geochemical properties of saline meadow saz soils and solonchaks common in the Fergana Valley is one of the pressing problems. There are more than 833 million hectares of saline land in the world, accounting for 8.7% of the earth's surface. Saline soils are distributed mainly in countries with a dry climate, in Pakistan, India, China, the USA, Central Asia, South America, Africa, Australia over large areas, as well as among non-saline soils in the form of spots in smaller areas. Saline soils in the CIS account for 52.3 million hectares, or 2.4% of all soils by area. More than half of the irrigated areas of Central Asia and Southern Kazakhstan, about 75–80% of irrigated lands have varying degrees of salinity. The purpose of the study is to study the content of salts and their migration in irrigated soils and salt marshes with varying degrees of salinity, common in the desert zone of the Fergana Valley.

Materials and research methods

Field soil research was carried out on the basis of Dokuchaev's morphological method and the comparative geographical research method. The analyzes were performed using the generally accepted method described in the SoyuzNIHI manuals [1], E.V. Arinushkina [2]. The results obtained were analyzed mathematically and statistically based on the methodological manual by B.A. Dospheva [3], computer technology of the latest versions of spreadsheets, graphs and Excel programs was used.

Research results and discussion

The study of the composition and amount of carbonates and sulfate salts in soils distributed in Central Fergana, which is part of the desert region of the Fergana Valley, is of great theoretical and practical importance. These salts have the ability to actively move along the soil profile and, as a result of their movement, accumulate at certain depths. A.F. Middendorf in his work presented the first classification of soils in the Fergana Valley: “pebble desert”, “salt desert”, “sandy desert”, “loess” and several humus discharges, different in conditions of agricultural use and yield, gave a comparative assessment of soils. He equated the fertile soils of Turkestan with black soils. A.F. Middendorf, giving a natural-historical description of the Fergana Valley, mentioned the presence of saline soils. In these areas, the role of mineralized groundwater located near the surface of the earth in the occurrence of these processes was scientifically proven mainly by the fact that these waters were under strong pressure [4]. In the work of V.A. Kovda provides information on the salt regime of saline soils in the Fergana region, the composition and dynamics of salts in soil solutions.

Soil cover of the Fergana Valley M.A. Pankov divided into 7 geomorphological and 13 soil regions. The characteristics of soil cover, mechanical composition, salinity and soil-forming rocks, parameters of underground groundwater, small geomorphological areas within soil regions are given. In addition, he expressed an opinion about the soils of the Central Fergana desert zone, which can be developed in the future, and reclamation measures for their development. In 1978–1988 M. Muhammadjonov and P. Besedin conducted experiments to improve the reclamation state of fertile and gypsum-filled soils of the Fergana Valley, that is, to cultivate agricultural crops by deep loosening. M.U. Umarov, studying the physical, physico-mechanical properties of soils in Central Fergana, emphasizes the presence of dense impermeable layers between 70–120 cm, and this layer negatively affects the physical properties of soils. Changes in the soils of Central Fergana under the influence of irrigation were studied in detail by A. Makhsudov in 1969–1979.

A high level of soil carbonation increases its buffering capacity, creating a permanent slightly alkaline environment. These salts, i.e. CaCO_3 , MgCO_3 , $\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ continuously supply and saturate the soil absorption complex of Ca and Mg. Thus, carbonates and sulfates of Ca and Mg in the soil have an important genetic significance and affect the effectiveness of applying phosphorus fertilizers to the soil, including taking part in the transition of phosphorus from easily mobile to poorly soluble forms. S.N. Ryzhov, according to their data, Ca and Mg carbonates participate in the cementation (compaction) of soil aggregates and aggregate formation. G.I. Olo-vyanishnikov, D.M. Kuguchkov in their work proved that these salts accumulate in the soil at different levels and cause carbonate salinization.

Fig. 1. Distribution of salts in old irrigated meadow saz soils, %

Rice. 2. Distribution of salts in salt marshes, %

CaCO₃ and MgCO₃, and the presence of increased amounts of MgSO₄ and MgCO₃ in the studied soils indicates the presence of a separate magnesium geochemical province (Fig. 1–2). However, the correlation between CaCO₃ and MgCO₃ is positive and low, 0.21–0.48. In this case, the error of the correlation coefficient (mr) is 0.34. In the territory of Central Fergana, which belongs to the desert region of the Fergana Valley, groundwater is mineralized (sulfate, hydrocarbonate) and located close to the surface of the earth. Gypsum and carbonates are in layer "B", i.e. 60–100 cm, forms sediment. This feature is especially good for evaporation barriers: according to M.A. Glazovskaya, they

can accumulate up to 25–30% carbonates. accumulate up to 25–30% carbonates. The more salts Na₂SO₄ and NaCl are in the soil solution (in the authors' studies there is enough Na₂SO₄), the solubility of carbonates slightly increases, and in the form of bicarbonates they reach the upper layers of the earth and due to their loss, water falls into the soil at high temperatures Based on the salts CaCO₃ and MgCO₃, we can agree with the conclusion that carbonates appear in the arable layer. According to available data, the amount of carbonates in salt crusts is 10–20%. Our observations confirm this number (16%). Biogenic lime is very rare in the studied soils; if it is present, it can be formed during sulfate reduction of sulfur in gypsum as follows:

According to M.A. Glazovskaya, this process is observed in salt marshes. The processes of formation of soil carbonates are complex, they also include carbonates of microelements, that is, microelements such as Cu, Sn, Rb, Mn, Hg, Zn accumulate in the carbonate layer. In conclusion, it should be noted that irrigated meadows -saz soils in the territory of Central Fergana belong to the desert region of the Fergana Valley, are poor in humus and nutrients, moderately saline, the average amount of harmful (toxic) salts in them is 0.6–0.7%.%. With an increase in the irrigation period, the amount of these salts decreases to 0.25–0.40% in old irrigated soils. Rich in gypsum and carbonates. MgSO₄ occupies a leading place in the composition of salts, which indicates the existence of a special provinciality. The top layer of newly irrigated soils is slightly saline (5–7% relative to the absorption capacity of absorbed Na), the remaining layers, both newly and old irrigated, are not saline. The adsorption of TSC cations in irrigated soils depends on their ionic radius.

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